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Exploring Teachers' Perceptions and Challenges in the Implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum: Insights for Improved Educational Practices

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Abstract.

The MATATAG Curriculum has been introduced as part of educational reforms aimed at improving student learning outcomes and teacher effectiveness. This research explores teachers' perceptions of the MATATAG Curriculum, examining its impact, challenges, and potential for enhancing educational quality. Using a quantitative approach, this study incorporates survey data from select teachers assigned to grade levels currently implementing the aforementioned curriculum. The findings highlight teachers' attitudes, concerns, and recommendations for optimizing the implementation of the curriculum.

Keywords: MATATAG Curriculum, teachers' perceptions, educational reform, curriculum development, pedagogy